

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

Rakhmatova Z.

MDIS in Tashkent,

Part-time teacher/lecturer of Banking and Finance School

Abstract

This scientific article examines the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan in the modern era and their content in order to introduce the green economy in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: green development, green economy, "P4G", UN Sustainable Development Goals, global environmental problems, Uzbekistan's transition to a "green economy".

Introduction

Today, humanity is facing new threats. The world's population continues to grow, while natural resources are constantly shrinking. It is said that such disproportion puts the countries of the world in a difficult situation. First of all, we are observing the aggravation of global environmental problems. Experts emphasize the need to introduce the principles of "green development" in the world economy in order to correct the situation. This approach is reflected in the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

It is known that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a high technical potential for energy production from renewable sources, 97% of which corresponds to the share of solar energy. With the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 22, 2019 No. PD-4422 "On rapid measures to increase the energy efficiency of economic sectors and the social sector, introduce energy-saving technologies and develop renewable energy sources", in order to effectively use the existing potential until 2030 the task of increasing

the share of renewable energy sources to more than 25% of the total volume of electricity production was set. For this, it is planned to build solar power plants with a total capacity of 5000 MW within 10 years [1].

The conducted analyzes showed that there are interrelated problems and needs in ensuring an efficient, resource-efficient and ecologically safe economy in the face of climate change. In particular, accelerating industrialization and population growth are significantly increasing the economy's need for resources, as well as intensifying the negative anthropogenic impact on the environment and leading to an increase in greenhouse gas emissions [2].

In 2019, Uzbekistan adopted the "Strategy of Transition to Green Economy". In the next ten years, the country plans to drastically reduce carbon consumption, introduce environmentally friendly and resource-saving technologies in all sectors of the economy, and widely use renewable, efficient energy sources

Figure 1. Goals of Strategy of Transition to Green Economy [5]

The priority directions of the strategy are as follows:

Improvement of energy efficiency of the basic sectors of the economy (covers the fields of electric power, heat energy, oil and gas industry, chemical industry);

Diversification of the consumption of energy resources and development of the use of renewable energy sources (includes the sectors of renewable energy sources, construction and use of buildings, transport, production of building materials);

Adapting to and mitigating the consequences of climate change, increasing the efficiency of natural resource use and protecting natural ecosystems (includ-

ing water and agriculture, forestry, solid waste, mitigating the negative effects of the ecological crisis in the Aral Bay);

Development of financial and non-financial mechanisms for supporting the “green” economy (development of institutional foundations for the introduction of green technologies, improvement of the legal framework in the field of “green” economy, development of energy efficiency regulation and control mechanisms, principles of “green” economy integration of education and science, capacity building and creation of a favorable environment for the transition to the “Green” economy, support of “Green” investments) [3].

Figure 2. The priority directions of the strategy [6]

The transition to a “green economy” will bring many bonuses to Uzbekistan. Therefore, I consider the 2019 Strategy, which initiated reforms in the sector, to be a very timely decision. The government aims to restore pre-pandemic macroeconomic indicators and achieve higher growth rates in the coming years. In turn, the country’s population and income are increasing. In such conditions, the demand for energy resources will increase. An important component of the “green economy” is the creation and use of renewable energy sources. In this regard, the potential of Uzbekistan is very high. According to the calculations of international financial institutions, the annual reserve of alternative energy (especially solar energy) in the republic is equivalent to 270 million tons of conventional fuel. This is three times more than our real need. Moreover, the implementation of projects in the field of “green energy” will allow to increase the share of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan by more than 3 times in the next ten years. This is an unprecedented benefit to the economy.

Research shows that Uzbekistan loses at least 4.5% of its GDP every year due to the use of hydrocarbon energy – oil, gas, coal. In addition, about half of the country’s power generation capacity is obsolete. Their restoration or modernization requires a lot of money. Instead, it is much better to switch to “green energy”, which is considered to be both economically and environmentally efficient. After all, the whole world is choosing this path. It is noteworthy that Uzbekistan was the first among the Central Asian countries to join this movement. In essence, the “Strategy of Transition to Green Economy” adopted two years ago means that our country is moving towards “green development” [4].

Of course, the “green economy” does not consist only of reforming the energy sector. It includes multifaceted and wide-ranging measures such as clean drinking water problems, food security, agricultural innovations, sustainable cities, rational waste management, expansion of forest areas, reduction of desertification.

Another important note. “Green economy” benefits not the state or business, but above all ordinary people. That is its social importance.

It is known from the world experience that the introduction of “green technologies” in various sectors of the economy has a positive effect on the quality of life of the population. As a result, life in cities becomes easier, infant mortality decreases, life expectancy increases, etc. In some regions of Latin America and Africa, the flow of external migration has decreased and the development of human capital has been observed.

It should not be forgotten that Uzbekistan joined the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement on Climate. Both documents place obligations on national governments to meet the requirements of “green development”. So, sooner or later we have to move to the “green economy” anyway. We have no other choice.

Internal and external problems of varying intensity are inevitable. A strategy has also been adopted for their preparedness and timely response.

Before transitioning to the “green economy”, it is necessary to audit the national legislation, adapt it to global requirements and bring it into a unified system. Some countries faced additional challenges as they started with practice and then dealt with the legal framework. Such an error slows down the transition process.

There are many inconsistencies and mutually exclusive aspects in our laws related to energy, science and innovation, tourism, which can be the driver of “green development”. The documentation itself is a lot. Let’s say that the mechanisms for delivering electricity to the consumer, setting the price, and making the payment are designed to match the existing traditional system. There are no legal norms that allow working with alternative energy sources. For example, who produces solar or other types of renewable energy and how much, in what order and at what rate is it delivered to the population? It is necessary to clarify such questions and reflect them in legal documents, and at the same time coordinate relations between new market entities.

The second important issue is to determine which financial instruments the state wants to use in the transition to the “green economy”. Because at the initial stage, it is necessary to make huge investments in economic sectors. Such a burden cannot be borne by the state budget, perhaps international donor organizations will be turned to. Then, under what conditions is foreign aid provided? Importantly, in what form can local beneficiaries – residents, business and economic entities – receive it? All efforts of the state will be wasted if business is not stimulated and motivated to work on the principles of “green economy”.

Usually, preferential or interest-free loans, subsidies and grants, and tax incentives are provided to enterprises and organizations, different segments of the population, for the use of alternative energy sources, reduction of carbon consumption in the production process, use of “green technologies” and purchase of relevant equipment. In turn, it is very important for the banking and financial system to show favor to this, and for banks to pay special attention to business projects related to the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The above-mentioned financial support instruments are appropriate if applied primarily to small business entities. The reason is that they are extremely sensitive to any change in market conditions and may not be able to adapt to the new competitive environment. Large enterprises have a “protective cushion”. Therefore, some companies have no difficulty in transitioning to the “green economy”. If not, it can minimize potential risks by diversifying the type of products or services.

Determining the sectors of the economy that play the main role in the transition to the “green economy” is also an urgent issue. In my opinion, this is the period when we invested in the tourism and service sectors at the initial stage. In addition, a great effect can be expected from the machine building and automobile industry. In a word, it is necessary for the state to decide now which sector, when and how to transfer to the “green economy”.

In the near future, we will also face the problem of shortage of qualified personnel, which is considered the intellectual strength of “green development”. Uzbekistan faces the challenge of training such specialists. If we do not start this work now, in the future we will be dependent on foreign countries and incur huge costs.

Rapid development of science and innovation is necessary for a faster and relatively painless transition to the “green economy”. Because this type of economy relies primarily on scientific achievements and effective innovative solutions. As just one example, the cost of using solar energy worldwide has fallen by 80 percent in the last decade. This trend continues.

Partnership for Green Growth and Global Goals (P4G) is a major international initiative launched in recent years. It can be called a special club of countries and cities that have chosen the path of “green development”. Now the project has more than ten members. Within the framework of this platform, participants will collaborate on creating innovative solutions that will help transition to the “green economy” [7].

“P4G” is an institutionalized structure, supported by a number of prestigious international associations and financial institutions. With its help, Uzbekistan can attract the necessary investments in the implementation of the “Green Economy” strategy. Above, I emphasized that “green economy” primarily serves the interests and prospects of ordinary people. Our participation in the “P4G” partnership will ultimately lead to improvement of the lifestyle of Uzbeks, increase in the quality of life, livability of cities, restoration of ecological balance in our region and many other positive changes [8].

Large companies, multinational corporations are implementing the principles of “green development” in their activities. They deliberately demonstrate their commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals to maintain their corporate image. In turn, the countries that have chosen the path of “green growth” are attracting the attention of international organizations and business circles. Foreign lenders and investors prefer to invest in these countries. Uzbekistan’s transition to a “green economy” is an important signal for the world community. It is not surprising that major donor organizations, especially Western companies, express their

desire to finance important investment projects aimed at the realization of our goals in terms of "green development".

References

1. Decision No. PQ-4422 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 22, 2019 "On rapid measures to increase the energy efficiency of economic sectors and the social sphere, introduce energy-saving technologies and develop renewable energy sources". <https://lex.uz/docs/4486125>
2. <https://gov.uz/uz/news/view/26700>
3. STRATEGY of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period 2019-2030. <https://lex.uz/docs/4539502>
4. How will Uzbekistan's "Green Economic Strategy" be implemented? <https://www.uzanalytics.com/iqtisodi%D0%B5t/9449/>
5. Kurpayanidi K. I. Actual problems of implementation of investment industrial entrepreneurial potential //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 301-307.
6. Khasanovna V. M. Current Tendency of Innovative Activity in the Country and //Journal of Accounting and Finance. – 2019. – Т. 19. – №. 1. – С. 53.
7. The 17 goals. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
8. Khasanovna V. M. APPROACH OF CLUSTERES IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES WITH HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 25.10. – С. 58-64.

СОЦІАЛЬНА ІНКЛЮЗІЯ: ДОСЯГНЕННЯ І ОСНОВНІ ЗАВДАННЯ ВОЄННОГО ПЕРІОДУ

Заяць Т.А.

*Доктор економічних наук, професор
Інститут демографії та соціальних досліджень
ім. М.В. Птухи НАН України
ORCID 0000-0002-9767-5527*

Заяць В.С.

*кандидат економічних наук, старший науковий співробітник
Інституту демографії та соціальних досліджень
ім. М.В. Птухи НАН України
ORCID 0000-0001-5757-9613*

SOCIAL INCLUSION: ACHIEVEMENTS AND MAIN TASKS OF MILITARY PERIOD

Zaiats T.,

*Dr. Sc. (Economics), Prof.,
Ptoukha Institute for Demography and Social Studies
of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*

Zaiats V.

*PhD in Economics, Senior Researcher
Ptoukha Institute for Demography and Social Studies
of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*

Анотація

У статті розглянуто проблеми соціальної інклюзії, які виникають на місцевому рівні, та можливі шляхи їх вирішення у найближчій перспективі. З'ясовано напрями поліпшення їх інформаційного забезпечення на основі створення відповідних реєстрів, що дасть змогу забезпечити адресність та територіальну доступність соціальних послуг. Визначено умови, необхідні для успішної соціальної інклюзії на місцевому рівні із залученням інститутів суспільства, влади, громадяни, бізнесу. Розглянуто зміни у системі надання послуг у зв'язку із воєнними діями в Україні, а також світовий досвід у цій сфері із залученням волонтерів, громадських і благодійних організацій.

Abstract

The article examines individual problems of social inclusion that arise at the local level, and possible ways to solve them in the near future. The directions for improving the information provision of social inclusion based on the creation of appropriate registers have been determined, which will make it possible to ensure the targeting and territorial availability of services. The conditions, necessary to ensure social inclusion at the local level with the involvement of society institutions, authorities, citizens, and businesses have been established. Changes in the system of providing services in connection with the military actions in Ukraine, as well as the experience of the countries of the world regarding achievements in the field of social inclusion with the involvement of volunteers, public and charitable organizations, were considered.

Ключові слова: доступність, соціальна інклюзія, соціальні послуги, соціальний розвиток громад, волонтерство.

Keywords: accessibility, social inclusion, social services, social development of communities, volunteering.